

**METHODS OF IMPROVING PROFESSIONAL MEDICAL
COMMUNICATION SKILLS****Satvaldiyev Ihtiyarjon Umarjanovich**

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Good doctors patients with efficient communication do - they of patients problems more precisely determine and patients to them being shown from help satisfied will be But it is necessary communication abilities how and doctors them how to get can

Doctors communication abilities efficient if they use , they , their patients also benefit brings First , doctors own of patients problems more precisely determine . Secondly , their patients their from care satisfaction harvest does and their problems , inspections and treatment methods better understand takes Third , patients to treatment more compliance they do and behavior change according to to recommendations action they do Fourth , patients concerns and their worry and to depression relatively weakness decreases . Finally , doctors own welfare will improve . We are doctors own patients with necessary level communication not doing about evidence we bring and of this possible has been reasons seeing we go out We are also efficient communication to do for necessary has been skills we describe and doctors this to skills how have to be possible discussion we do

In communication disadvantages

Good doctors perform need has been patients with communication of doing main duties shows . Unfortunately , doctors most of the time this tasks do it they can't . Patients complaints and of worries only half to be determined can Most of the time doctors of patients own problems perception reach or of problems physical , emotional and social effect about less information they take. Doctors information when they give this they do flexible didn't happen way and individual patients to know wanted things careless to leave inclined They are of patients to them what was said How good that they understood to check not so much attention They do not give. In patients psychological of diseases from half at least is determined. Most of the time patients doctor by recommendation done treatment and recommendations , as well as the patient satisfaction level compliance they do n't variable will be

CONCLUSIONS

Summary by doing that's it to say maybe good communication ability have doctors of patients problems more precisely determine

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Their patients psychological in terms of better adapts and their from care more satisfied

Good communication to do ability have has been doctors from work satisfaction increase and at work stress reduce

Communication skills to teach efficient methods there is

Main skills exercise to do and work about constructive feedback get opportunity very important

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